

Driving innovation through advanced semiconductor materials and a global collaborative ecosystem

Best practice category

Materials, chemicals and equipment; Partner collaboration and open ecosystems; Strengthening manufacturing capacities

Stakeholder group

Large enterprises, semiconductor manufacturers

Value chain position

Materials production, R&D, Fabless & Foundry support

General Information

Soitec is a French company founded in the 1980s in the important high-tech innovative environment of Grenoble in France. Soitec is a leader in the development and production of advanced semiconductor materials, offering innovative solutions with the main feature of reducing energy consumption, an important challenge nowadays, and also improving circuit performance. Its global importance is given by the massive presence of Soitec products in billions of devices and in most smartphones today, the company also serves sectors such as automotive, industrial, smart devices and artificial intelligence. The company developed Smart Cut™ technology, the best-known of Soitec's portfolio, which forms the basis of the vast majority of the company's products. The group is also a global giant in the production of silicon-on-insulator (SOI) wafers, while also including substrates based on gallium nitride (GaN) and silicon carbide (SiC). In addition, Soitec has a global presence with production sites and sales offices in **Europe, Asia and America**, allowing strategic proximity to customers and rapid adaptation to the needs of growing markets.

Activities and best practices

- Soitec promotes innovation through the development of cutting-edge semiconductor materials and collaboration with top-notch universities and research centers. The company carries out a research collaboration with MIT's Microsystems Technology Laboratories, also participating in the Industrial Advisory Board for Strategic Directions in Microelectronics. In Europe, Soitec has strategic partnerships with institutions such as IMEC, CEA-Leti and Fraunhofer. An example is the SmartSiC™ technology launched in 2023, developed in collaboration with the Substrate Innovation Centre co-founded by Soitec and CEA-Leti. The company also maintains relationships with universities such as **Stanford, UC-Berkeley, the National University of Singapore (NUS)**, strengthening the sharing of know-how and the development of advanced materials. Furthermore, initiatives such as the collaboration with the Institut Universitaire de Technologie 1 of the Université Grenoble Alpes demonstrate how Soitec directly involves the academic world in the formation of new skills, also offering structured programmes for production operators and managers to support professional growth and technical and managerial skills. In the semiconductor industry, connectivity and the talent pool are essential: The success of Soitec is also driven by the talent and diversity of its 2,300 employees, representing **50 nationalities** and working at sites in **Europe, the United States, and Asia**. This ensures technical know-how, innovation, and a global presence.

- Soitec plays a key role in making the European chip industry more autonomous. Since 2018, the company has been the protagonist of the IPCEI program for microelectronics, a fundamental tool that allows financing innovation throughout the entire supply chain. But Soitec does more than just participate: it also coordinates ambitious projects such as BEYOND5, created specifically to build a European supply chain based on RFSOI technology, important for the future of 5G and advanced sensors. Another important project is Transform project, an initiative that networks 33 partners across the EU to build a European silicon carbide (SiC) supply chain. Thanks to the Substrate Innovation Centre's work on prototyping and close collaborations across the supply chain, Soitec is able to transform advanced materials such as SmartSiC™ and SOI into industrial standards, giving Europe a real technological advantage.

Challenges addressed with this practice

Soitec's approach addresses the industry's most pressing challenges by focusing on collaboration: by overcoming the limitations of traditional silicon, the company offers materials that improve chip performance while reducing consumption. Its active participation in European projects is not only formal, but serves to build true technological sovereignty, networking with partners to secure the supply of critical materials for cars and telephony. This exchange of knowledge with universities and research centers helps train the talent needed to fill the shortage of specialised technicians. Finally, by sharing industry standards and prototyping models, Soitec lowers the risks and costs of research, accelerating the move towards more sustainable and independent electronics.